

NAYREC-2023

NAYREC 2023 Conference Program

10th National Young Researchers Conference 2023

May 25th 2023

Date	Hour	Event
25/05/2023	8:45-9:15	Registration
	9:30-11:00	Opening Ceremony at Conference Hall: 302 Education Building
	9:35-9:40	Introducing the Event
	9:40-9:45	National Anthem
	9:45-9:50	Promotional Videos
	9:50-10:00	Welcome Speech by Dr. Idris Hadi , Head of Board of Trustees, or Dr. Abdul Samad Salahuddin The President, Tishk International University
	10:00-10:05	Speech of Minister
	10:05-10:10	Welcoming Speech: Conference Chair
	10:05-10:10	Opening Address by Muhammed S. Anwar, Conference Chair, Tishk International University.
	10:10-10:15	Awarding Plaque to the Sponsor and Keynote Speaker
	10:15-10:45	Keynote Speaker: Dr. Abdullah Kurudirek Title: Teaching Generation Z & Generation Alpha
	10:45-11:00	Coffee Break
	11:00-12:30	I. Concurrent Session
	12:30-14:00	Lunch
	14:00-15:30	II. Concurrent Session
	15:30-16:00	Coffee Break
	16:00-16:30	Closing Ceremony Conference Hall (302)

Keynote Speaker

Teaching Generation Z & Generation Alpha

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ABSTRACT

Traditional repetitive teaching is being replaced with effective and technologically enhanced teaching and learning approaches that involve the students' active participation. In today's digital age, educational institutions can supplement a more dynamic learning environment for students by offering the appropriate materials. This presentation is focused on the educational transformation and technology acceptance of Generation Z and Generation Alpha. I'll focus on the critical components of teaching the Alpha and Z generations.

Keywords: *Z Generation, Alpha Generation, Teaching, Education.*